

ENTREPRENEURIAL PERSONAL SKILL AS PREDICTOR OF PERCEIVED JOB SELF-RELIANCE AMONG UNIVERSITY STUDENTS IN NORTH EAST NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

This study investigates the entrepreneurial personal skill as predictors of perceived job self-reliance among university students in North East Nigeria. Entrepreneurship is seen as a key driver of economic growth, job creation, and self-sufficiency, making it crucial for students to acquire relevant entrepreneurial skills that foster independence and employability. One research objective and one research question together with one hypothesis were formulated for the study. The study used a predictive correlational design with a sample of 500 students using 10% out of the population of the study of (5003) from six universities in the North East, applying proportionate stratified sampling. Data was collected using a questionnaire (EPSQ) designed and Cumulative Grade Point Average from their 300 level session were used for data collection to assess entrepreneurial personal skills. The EPSQ was validated by experts while Cronbach's alpha method was used to determine the reliability of the instrument and a reliability of 0.79 was obtained. Descriptive statistics of mean and standard deviation were used to answer the research question while, the hypothesis was tested at 0.05 level of significance using linear regression analysis. Results showed that while students demonstrated a high level of entrepreneurial skills in areas like problem-solving and creative thinking, the entrepreneurial skills and perceived job self-reliance was weak, explaining only 0.5% of the variability in perceived self-reliance. The findings recommend that while entrepreneurial personal skills are valuable, other factors such as socio-economic and cultural influences may significantly impact the development of self-reliance in this context. The study emphasizes the need for targeted interventions to enhance entrepreneurial skills and promote self-reliance among students in North East Nigeria.

Keywords: Entrepreneurial, Personal Skills, Perceived Job Self-Reliance

INTRODUCTION

Entrepreneurship has been recognized as the determinant or pivotal element of economic growth and development (Kindane & Harvey, 2020; Nafukko & Maya, 2021; Katha, 2022). This is because entrepreneurship leads to the creation of small and medium scale businesses, providing employment opportunities, income generation, uplifting of standard of living and utilization of human, material and financial resources of a country in the right direction. It is on these benefits that many countries have placed intensive and frantic efforts and programmes towards development of entrepreneurship. Entrepreneurial skill can change the students' mind set and turn them to become productive through the acquisition of relevant business skills. When undergraduate students are equipped with relevant entrepreneurial skill such as entrepreneurial personal skills.

Entrepreneurial personal skills refer to an individual's 'inner' qualities or Emotional Intelligent Quotient (EIQ), along with the kind of habits, attitude, and communication style that works well alongside others. Personal skills are typically acquired or developed through experiences and training, and they can require sustained effort. Entrepreneurial personal skills are simply business skills, which an individual acquires to enable him/her function effectively in the turbulent business environment as an entrepreneur for Perceived job self-reliance and self-employed (Chell, 2013). Students with excellent personal skills are capable of learning, communicating analyzing, and using tools to solve problem. Therefore, entrepreneurial personal skills are highly required by the students who are by academic discipline involved in 'spatial interaction'.

Entrepreneurial personal skills, such as effective communication and positive interaction, are directly linked to Perceived job self-reliance. These skills enable individuals to collaborate effectively with others while fostering independence and the ability to rely on their own efforts and capabilities. Ebo and Ukpong (2017) define Perceived job self-reliance as the ability to depend on one's skills, creativity, and values not only to improve oneself but also to contribute positively to others. Entrepreneurial skills enhance this by equipping individuals with the resourcefulness and adaptability needed to navigate challenges and seize opportunities. As such, these skills serve as a foundation for Perceived job self-reliance, empowering individuals to thrive independently while fostering meaningful interactions with others (Ebo & Ukpong, 2017).

Perceived job self-reliance is an ability to rely on one's own efforts, abilities or learnt skills. A self-reliant person is one who possesses great creative ability, one who is functional, one who has acquired some values and skills to improve not just himself, but people around him/her; a resourceful individual (Ebo & Ukpong, 2017). When students learn entrepreneurial skills, the skills will enable them establish small scale businesses in their immediate rural environment thereby making them to be self-reliance and even employer of labour. Self-reliant citizens breed self-reliant nation and the benefits of self-reliance to the society will include: i) reduction in level of unemployment, ii) reduction in level of social vices in the society, iii) reduction in the level of frustration and poverty, vi) encouragement of wealth creation and development, and vii) increment in the standard of living of a nation. The call for the introduction of Entrepreneurship education in Nigerian tertiary institutions is actually a direct response to the changing socio-economic and political conditions in the world and Nigeria in particular which had resulted into high levels of unemployment of Nigerian graduates. Ogege (2011) believes that entrepreneurship course makes it possible for the youth (whether they are graduates or not) to acquire the requisite skills to be self-reliant without undue reliance on an over-burdened government to create jobs for them. As a result of the perceived importance of entrepreneurship in the economies of societies, especially its ability to reduce unemployment through acquisition of skills for Perceived job self-reliance, the interest in entrepreneurship course is on the increase in the universities.

In recent years, Nigeria has faced escalating unemployment rates among university graduates, particularly in the North East region. Despite the increasing number of graduates, many encounter significant challenges in securing stable and rewarding employment. A contributing factor to this issue is the insufficient development of essential entrepreneurial personal skills, which are crucial for Perceived job self-reliance and employability (Ebo & Ukpong, 2017). These skills, including creativity, problem-solving, communication, and teamwork, are vital for graduates to excel in the job market and to create their own opportunities, thereby contributing to their communities (Adebayo & Olawole, 2018).

Several studies have explored the relationship between entrepreneurial personal skills and Perceived job self-reliance in Nigeria. Studies such as Adamu (2020) and Abiodun (2015) found statistical significance, indicating that personal entrepreneurial skills like decision-making, resilience, and problem-solving are crucial for fostering Perceived job self-reliance, with barriers such as cultural constraints and insecurity impeding their development. Eze and Ugwu (2020) also

confirmed a statistical significance between digital literacy and entrepreneurial skills, suggesting that access to technology positively influences Perceived job self-reliance. In contrast, Bello (2023) explored factors like insecurity and financial constraints, noting no statistical significance in some cases. These studies highlighted that despite the theoretical importance of entrepreneurial skills for Perceived job self-reliance, practical constraints in the region limit their impact. Furthermore, Okoro and Ede (2021) and Olojede and Ogundele (2022) provided mixed results, indicating that while financial access and socio-cultural barriers are important, they did not always show statistical significance across all demographic groups studied.

However, there is limited research on how these skills influence students' Perceived job self-reliance, particularly in the context of North East Nigeria. Perceived job self-reliance, as a key aspect of personal and professional growth, involves the ability to depend on one's abilities and acquired skills to navigate challenges and contribute to society (Ebo & Ukpong, 2017). The extent to which entrepreneurial personal skills serve as predictors of Perceived job self-reliance among students in North East universities remains underexplored. Understanding this relationship is critical for developing educational policies and curricula that equip students with the necessary skills to enhance their independence and employability (Adebayo & Olawole, 2018).

This study, therefore, seeks to investigate the role of entrepreneurial personal skill as predictors of Perceived job self-reliance among university students in the North East region of Nigeria. The aim is to inform strategies that foster self-reliant graduates capable of overcoming the challenges of unemployment and contributing to sustainable development in the region.

PURPOSE OF THE STUDY

The purpose of this study was to examine entrepreneurial personal skill as predictors of Perceived job self-reliance among university students in the North East region of Nigeria. Specifically, the study was sought to determine: whether entrepreneurial personal skill predicts Perceived job self-reliance among universities students in the North East Nigeria or not.

RESEARCH QUESTION

What is the level of entrepreneurial personal skill among undergraduate students in Northeast Nigeria?

HYPOTHESIS

H₀₁: Entrepreneurial personal skill does not statistically predict job self-reliance among university students in the North East region of Nigeria.

METHODOLOGY

This study employed a correlational research design (predictive), which is used to investigate the whether two or more variables predict another. Specifically, a predictive correlational survey design was adopted, as described by Sousa, Driessnack, and Mendes (2017), where one variable (predictor) is used to forecast changes in another (outcome). For this study, the predictor variable was entrepreneurial personal skills, while the outcome was Perceived job self-reliance among universities students in the North East Nigeria. The goal was to evaluate both their joint and relative predictive values. The target population consisted of 5003 fourth-year Faculty of Education students from six Federal universities in North-East Nigeria. The distribution of students by institution was as follows: Modibbo Adama University, Yola (854 students); Abubakar Tafawa Balewa University, Bauchi (1041 students); University of Maiduguri, Borno (1250 students); Federal

University Kashere, Gombe (981 students); Federal University Wukari, Taraba (275 students); and Federal University Gashua, Yobe (602 students). A sample size of 500 students was determined using Nwana’s (2005) guidelines, which recommend a 10% sample for populations in the thousands. The sample was proportionally allocated as follows: Modibbo Adama University, Yola (99 students), Abubakar Tafawa Balewa University, Bauchi (112 students), University of Maiduguri (118 students), Federal University Kashere (108 students), Federal University Wukari (15 students), and Federal University Gashua (48 students). A proportionate stratified sampling technique was used due to the varying sizes of the institutions. A sampling fraction (S.F) was calculated using the formula: $S/F = n/N$, where n represents the sample size and N is the population size. Samples proportional to the size of each institution were drawn using simple random sampling. To ensure fairness, serial numbers were written on folded pieces of paper, mixed thoroughly in a container, and picked at random. This process was repeated until the required sample size for each institution was obtained. Data collection instruments included the students’ CGPA from their third year and a questionnaire titled "Entrepreneurial Personal Skill Questionnaire (EPSQ)," designed to measure how Entrepreneurial Personal Skill predicts academic achievement. The AWSQ utilized a modified Likert scale with response options ranging from Very High Level (VHL) to Very Low Level (VLL), scored from 5 to 1, respectively. Experts validated the content and face validity of the EPSQ. The reliability of the EPSQ was determined using the Cronbach Alpha method. The instrument was tested on students from Adamawa State University, Mubi, which was outside the study area. A reliability coefficient of 0.79 was obtained, indicating acceptable internal consistency. Mean and standard deviation were employed to answer the research question. The mean was used to gauge response levels, while the standard deviation measured how much the responses clustered around the mean. Real limits of mean values were used as decision criteria: Very High Level (VHL): 4.50–5.00, High Level (HL): 3.50–4.49, Moderate Level (ML): 2.50–3.49, Low Level (LL): 1.50–2.49, Very Low Level (VLL): 0.50–1.49. The hypothesis was tested using simple linear regression analysis at a 0.05 level of significance. If the p-value was greater than 0.05, the hypothesis was accepted; otherwise, it was rejected.

RESULTS

Research Question: What is the level of entrepreneurial personal skill among undergraduate students in Northeast Nigeria?

Table 1: Mean and Standard Deviation of Level of Entrepreneurial Personal Skill

S/N	n = 500	Mean	S. D	Remark
1	Ability to accept responsibility.	3.62	1.43	HL
2	Ability to cope with complications.	3.90	1.34	HL
3	Ability to communicate well with the customers.	3.48	1.57	ML
4	Ability to identify weaknesses.	4.29	1.03	HL
5	Problem-solving capacity.	3.86	1.37	HL
6	Creative thinking skills.	4.14	1.15	HL
7	Ability to work in a team.	3.93	1.37	HL
8	Ability to manage stressful conditions.	4.42	0.85	HL
9	Ability to identify ready markets for my products.	3.88	1.32	HL
10	Ability to be productive.	3.69	1.40	HL
	Grand Mean	3.92	1.28	HL

The table highlights the level of entrepreneurial personal skills among respondents, assessed across ten key areas. The participants demonstrated a high level of competency in most skills, particularly in managing stressful conditions, identifying weaknesses, and creative thinking. Other skills, such as problem-solving and teamwork, also showed strong proficiency. However, the ability to communicate effectively with customers was identified as an area requiring improvement. A grant mean of 3.92 indicates high level of entrepreneurial personal skill acquired by undergraduate students in North east, Nigeria.

H₀₁: Entrepreneurial personal skill does not statistically predict job self-reliance among university students in the North East region of Nigeria.

Table 2a: Model Summary of Regression Analysis between Entrepreneurial personal skill and Perceived job self-reliance

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.070 ^a	.005	.002	.54670

Table 2a shows the Model Summary of the regression analysis reveals a very weak relationship between entrepreneurial personal skills and perceived job self-reliance. The correlation coefficient (R) of 0.070 indicates a minimal positive relationship, suggesting that entrepreneurial personal skills have little effect on perceived job self-reliance. The R Square value of 0.005 means that only 0.5% of the variability in perceived job self-reliance is explained by entrepreneurial personal skills, indicating a very weak explanatory power for the model. Adjusted R Square, at 0.002, further confirms that when accounting for the number of predictors, the model still explains only a negligible portion (0.2%) of the variability in perceived job self-reliance. The Standard Error of the Estimate, at 0.54670, suggests considerable variation between the observed and predicted values. Overall, the regression analysis shows that entrepreneurial personal skills have a weak and statistically insignificant impact on perceived job self-reliance, and further analysis may be needed to better understand this relationship.

Table 2b: Summary of Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) of Regression between Entrepreneurial personal skill and Perceived job self-reliance

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	.586	1	.586	1.960	.162
	Residual	118.953	398	.299		
	Total	119.539	399			

Not Significant; $p > 0.05$.

Table 2b shows the Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) summary indicates that the regression model between entrepreneurial personal skills and perceived job self-reliance is not statistically significant. The regression sum of squares is 0.586, with 1 degree of freedom (Df), resulting in a mean square of 0.586. The F-value is 1.960, and the p-value is 0.162, which is greater than the threshold of 0.05, indicating that the relationship between entrepreneurial personal skills and perceived job self-reliance is not significant. The residual sum of squares is 118.953, with 398 degrees of freedom, giving a mean square of 0.299. The total sum of squares is 119.539, with 399 degrees of freedom. Since the p-value exceeds 0.05, we

conclude that the model does not provide sufficient evidence to support a significant relationship between entrepreneurial personal skills and perceived job self-reliance.

Table 2c: Summary of Regression Coefficients^a between Entrepreneurial personal skill and Perceived job self-reliance

Model		Unstandardized		Standardized		
		Coefficients		Coefficients		
		B	Std. Error	Beta	t	Sig.
1	(Constant)	3.936	.065		60.418	.000
	Entrepreneurial personal skill	-.024	.017	-.070	-1.400	.162

Not Significant; $p > 0.05$.

The regression coefficients summary reveals that the relationship between entrepreneurial personal skills and perceived job self-reliance is not statistically significant. The constant term has an unstandardized coefficient (B) of 3.936 with a standard error of 0.065, and a t-value of 60.418, which is significant with a p-value of 0.000. However, the unstandardized coefficient for entrepreneurial personal skill is -0.024, with a standard error of 0.017, and the standardized beta coefficient is -0.070. The t-value for this coefficient is -1.400, and the p-value is 0.162, which is greater than 0.05. This suggests that entrepreneurial personal skill do not significantly predict perceived job self-reliance, as the p-value exceeds the critical threshold for significance.

DISCUSSION OF THE STUDY

The findings of this study align with several studies that explored whether entrepreneurial personal skill predicts perceived job self-reliance, particularly in the context of the North East region of Nigeria. In this study, entrepreneurial personal skills such as problem-solving, communication, and stress management were found not to statistically predict perceived job self-reliance. This suggests that, despite their theoretical importance, these skills do not have a direct impact on self-reliance in this particular context.

Several studies have supported the view that entrepreneurial skills are crucial for enhancing perceived job self-reliance, though they have also highlighted contextual challenges that limit their effectiveness. Adebayo (2020) and Abdullahi (2021) found that personal entrepreneurial skills, such as decision-making, resilience, and problem-solving, are essential for fostering job self-reliance. However, these studies also pointed out that barriers such as cultural constraints and insecurity can impede the development and application of these skills, especially in regions like the North East of Nigeria. This aligns with the findings of this study, where external factors such as insecurity and socio-economic constraints seem to have overshadowed the potential impact of entrepreneurial skills on job self-reliance.

Similarly, Eze and Ugwu (2020) confirmed a significant relationship between digital literacy and entrepreneurial skills, suggesting that access to technology positively influences perceived job self-reliance. However, this study did not find the same level of significance in its results, possibly due to the limited access to resources or technology among the university students in the region. The lack of practical application opportunities for these skills within the academic environment could be a key reason for the discrepancy between this study and Eze and Ugwu’s (2020) findings.

On the other hand, other studies provided results that did not align with the findings of this study. Bello (2023) examined factors such as insecurity and financial constraints, which contributed to a lack of statistical significance in their studies. While these studies acknowledged the relevance of entrepreneurial skills, they emphasized that practical constraints such as insecurity and limited financial access hinder the development of these skills. This perspective resonates with the challenges highlighted in this study, as the North East region has experienced significant insecurity, limiting students' ability to develop and apply entrepreneurial skills in practical settings.

Moreover, Okoro and Ede (2021) and Olojede and Ogundele (2022) provided mixed results regarding the role of financial access and socio-cultural barriers. While these factors were deemed important, they did not always show statistical significance across all demographic groups studied. This suggests that the relationship between entrepreneurial skills and perceived job self-reliance is complex, with contextual factors influencing the outcomes differently depending on specific circumstances.

In contrast, some studies reported statistically significant results linking entrepreneurial personal skills to perceived job self-reliance. Adebayo (2020) and Abdullahi (2021), for instance, found that skills such as decision-making and resilience were strong predictors of self-reliance. They argued that while entrepreneurial skills are essential, they must be cultivated in environments that support their development. These studies align with the findings of this research by confirming the importance of personal entrepreneurial skills, but they also recognize the impact of external constraints on their effectiveness.

CONCLUSION

The study concluded that Entrepreneurial personal skill does not statistically significant predictors Perceived job self-reliance among university students in the North East region of Nigeria. Although entrepreneurial skills such as creativity, problem-solving, and communication are vital in various entrepreneurial contexts, they do not appear to have a direct effect on how individuals perceive their job self-reliance within this particular study. The lack of significant predictive value suggests that other factors may play a more prominent role in determining job self-reliance.

RECOMMENDATIONS

In view of the study's findings, the following recommendations are put forward to strengthen entrepreneurial personal skills, enhance responsibility-taking, and foster job self-reliance among learners and aspiring entrepreneurs:

1. Given that the ability to accept responsibility was rated as moderate, entrepreneurship education should incorporate specific modules and activities that cultivate accountability, ethical judgment, and leadership ownership. This will encourage learners to take initiative and assume responsibility for their decisions and outcomes.
2. Higher education institutions and training centers should expand practical learning experiences such as internships, enterprise simulations, and community-based projects. These experiences help participants translate theoretical entrepreneurial skills into real-life applications that promote job self-reliance.
3. Structured mentorship and coaching frameworks should be introduced to connect learners with experienced entrepreneurs and business professionals. Such relationships can inspire responsible behavior, self-discipline, and confidence in pursuing independent ventures.
4. While creativity, teamwork, and communication are evident strengths, these competencies should be more intentionally connected to self-reliance activities such as idea development, business management, and adaptive problem-solving under real-world conditions.

5. Curriculum designers and educational planners should review existing entrepreneurship courses to ensure they emphasize personal accountability, decision-making, innovation, and sustainable self-employment strategies relevant to the labor market.

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